

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF NATURAL COUMARINS OF *TODDALIA ACULEATA*.

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From the stem-bark of *Toddalia aculeata* (I) aculeatin ($C_{18}H_{18}O_{15}$, m. p. 113°), (II) aculeatin hydrate ($C_{18}H_{20}O_{16}$, m. p. 150°), isomeric with toddalolactone, isolated by Dey and Pillay, and (III) a colourless substance, m. p. 239° , which has not been investigated, have been obtained. The reactions of aculeatin hydrate and toddalolactone are almost similar and they give rise to same oxidation products.

Toddalia Aculeata, Pers., (N.O. Rutaceae, Sub-family *Toddaloideae*) is a scandent shrub known to the Sanskrit writers as Kanchana (Golden) on account of the orange colour of its fruits and also called Dahana because of the pungency of its berries. The plant is distributed in the sub-tropical Himalayas from Kumaon eastwards to Bhutan at an elevation of 5,000 ft. and also in Western and Southern India and Ceylon.

The root known as Lopez root (*Toddalia radix*) has been used in the Indian Pharmacopoeia as a remedy of great value in constitutional debility and in convalescence after febrile and other exhaustive diseases. The fresh bark is administered by Tamil Physicians for the cure of a sort of remittent commonly known as "hill-fever."

Regarding the chemical constituents of Lopez root, Dymock, Warden and Hooper (*Pharmacographia Indica*, Vol. I, 261) mention the presence of a resin, essential oil (smell like oil of citron) and a bitter principle.

According to Hooper (*Schimmel's Berichte*, 1893, p. 64), the essential oil consists of citronellal, linalool, and a camphor-like substance, m. p. $96.5-97^{\circ}$. The bark has been found to contain resinous matter, bitter principle, tannin, citric acid, sugar, pectin, starch etc., and yields an ash rich in manganese (Schnitzer, *Vierteljahrsschr. Prakt. Pharm.*, 1862, 11, 1). An alkali-soluble glucoside believed to be hesperidin, has also been isolated (*Beih. Bot. C.*, 1902, 12, 55), but has later been proved to be diosmin (Osterle and Wander, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1927, 8, 519). Flückiger and Hanbury (*Pharmacographia Indica*, Vol. I, p. 262) could not detect berberine in the plant, but Perkin and Hümmel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 413) isolated a yellow, crystalline hydrochloride of an alkaloid from Lopez root, which they considered to be identical with berberin hydrochloride. Dey and Pillay (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1933, 271, 477) have isolated two different alkaloids from the same source and have named them toddalin and toddalinin.

Dey and Pillay (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1933, 271, 477 ; 1935, 273, 223) further isolated from the root bark a crystalline neutral compound toddalolactone, which has been further investigated by Späth, Dey and Tyray (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1825) and shown to have the structure (I).

(I)

The present work describes the constituents of the stem-bark, which is also used in medicine though to a limited extent. The bark was secured from the Darjeeling District (Bengal). Three different neutral compounds have been isolated from the stem-bark (*vide Experimental*):

(1) A colourless compound, m.p. 239°, neutral to litmus, insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali and indifferent towards alcoholic ferric chloride. A detailed investigation is not possible on account of its very poor yield (0.01%).

(2) The second compound, (0.06%) forming colourless plates, m.p. 113°, has been named aculeatin.

(3) A substance, m.p. 150°. It has been named aculeatin hydrate, since it is also obtained from aculeatin by prolonged treatment with dilute sulphuric acid at 100°.

The C—H values and the molecular weight show that aculeatin has the formula $C_{14}H_{12}O_5$. Methoxyl estimation by Zeisel-Pregl-Viebock technique proves the presence of two methoxyl groups in the molecule. Aculeatin is optically active, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ being -16.8° in ethyl acetate. It has lactonic properties, since although aculeatin is insoluble in aqueous alkali, it readily dissolves in alcoholic alkali and acids precipitate the original compound. Hence the formula of aculeatin can be written as

A characteristic property of coumarins is their capacity to undergo hydrolysis to a *trans*-acid when heated with alkali in presence of a trace of mercuric oxide (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247). Aculeatin is found to undergo hydrolysis forming a stable acid, $C_{14}H_{12}O_7$, m.p. 171°, under the usual experimental conditions. The formula of aculeatin may consequently be further expanded to (II) or (III),

(II)

(III)

The oxygen atom in the residue, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}-$ is not ketonic or aldehydic in character since aculeatin fails to condense with the usual reagents for ketones and aldehydes. The group $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}-$ has been found to occur in some natural coumarins in the form of dihydro isoprene oxide, as will be evident from an inspection of the formula of oxypeucedanin (IV), auraptin (V) and byak-angelicol (VI).

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

It may be further mentioned that the carbon atom in the glycide ring is asymmetric, and consequently all these compounds show optical activity. Another possibility is the formulation of aculeatin as (VII) or (VIII), where also asymmetric carbon atoms are present. The basic ring system of

(VII) (linear)

(VIII) (angular)

(VII) is present in nodakenin, but the angular type has not been discovered in natural products, although the possibility is not excluded.

The presence of the glycidic ring present in (IV), (V) or (VI) has been demonstrated by the hydrolysis of the compounds to the corresponding dihydroxy compounds $[\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2-]$ or conversion into the open chain system,

by means of hydrochloric acid gas. Compounds of the type (VII) and (VIII) are not known to undergo such ring-fission. Aculeatin, however, has been found to remain unaffected by treatment with 15% oxalic acid at 100° for 4 hours, but prolonged treatment with very dilute sulphuric acid at 100° effects a smooth hydrolysis to a colourless compound $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$, aculeatin hydrate, m. p. 150°, which is identical with the third substance. Hence aculeatin may be represented by (IX) and its hydrate by (X).

(IX)

(X)

Aculeatin hydrate and toddalolactone are isomeric compounds having the following properties.

TABLE I.

	Toddalolactone (Dey and Pillay)	Aculeatin hydrate (Present author)
M. p.	131-132.5°	150°
$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	+55°	+51°
(M. p.) Acid phthalate	181°	204°
(M. p.) Acid	178°	170.21°
„ Diacetyl	211-112°	127°

Aculeatin hydrate forms a diacetyl derivative showing the presence of two alcoholic OH groups. The fact that only one molecule of phthalic anhydride combines with one of aculeatin hydrate suggests that one of the two OH groups is tertiary in character.

Aculeatin hydrate is found to undergo degradation by means of chromic acid giving rise to acetone (identified as dibenzal acetone) indicating the presence of $\text{Me}_2\text{C}<$ group in the side chain. It will not be unreasonable to attach one OH group to the central C atom of the isopropyl group to make it tertiary, $\begin{matrix} \text{Me} \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Me} \end{matrix} \text{OH}$, to explain the formation of the mono acid-phthalate, and of acetone by degradative oxidation.

The position of the second OH group with respect to the tertiary OH group will depend on the nature of the oxide-ring in aculeatin, which may be formulated as a 1:2-oxide or 1:3-oxide as shown below:

1:2-Oxide

1:3-Oxide.

The former, however, would be expected to furnish a glycol $\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{-CHOH-CH}_2\text{-}$ and the latter a glycol $\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}(\text{OH})\text{-}$ on hydrolysis. Aculeatin hydrate furnishes on oxidation by Criegee's reagent (Criegee, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 260) a compound, m.p. $142^\circ\text{-}142.5^\circ$, which analyses for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$, and produces *p*-nitrophenyl hydrazone, m.p. 213° , and reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate, thus showing that aculeatin possesses the 1:2-oxide structure. The reactions of aculeatin hydrate and toddalolactone (Späth, Dey and Tyray, *loc. cit.*) are almost similar and they give rise to same oxidation products, e.g., the aldehyde (m.p. $141.5^\circ\text{-}142.5^\circ$, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 213°); and the ketone (m.p. 119° , semicarbazone, m. p. 206.9° , *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 209°), under the influence of fused zinc chloride or 2% hydrochloric acid at 140° .

A specimen of toddalolactone was obtained from Dr. B. B. Dey, to whom my best thanks are due, and the aldehyde and ketone obtained from it had identical m.p. (m.p. of the derivatives is also the same). The mixed melting points were also the same. The chemical evidence is definitely in favour of the identity of aculeatin hydrate and toddalolactone.

It has been possible to isolate a compound, m. p. 150° , from the sample of toddalolactone kindly supplied by Dr. B. B. Dey. The melting point of this remained undepressed when mixed with aculeatin hydrate (m.p. 150°). This suggests that either toddalolactone contains aculeatin hydrate as an impurity, or there is a possibility of a new type of isomerism which admits of a transformation from Dey's type to aculeatin hydrate by a simple process of recrystallisation from ethyl acetate and adding petroleum ether (b. p. $30-40^{\circ}$) as diluent, the process being repeated several times. It may here be remarked that repeated recrystallisations of aculeatin hydrate do not alter its m.p. (150°).

Whatever may be the causes of the difference between toddalolactone and aculeatin hydrate, there cannot be any doubt as to the correct structure of aculeatin, which must be represented by (XI).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Isolation of Aculeatin and Aculeatin hydrate.

Finely powdered dry stembark of the plant *Toddalia Aculeata* (Pers.) (1 Kg.) was extracted with ether for 16 hours in a Soxhlet apparatus and three neutral compounds were isolated from the ethereal extract.

(1) The filtered extract was concentrated to about 60 c.c., and ether (40 c.c.) added as diluent and this was kept in a frigidaire. Crystals began to appear after 3 day. After 13 days the crystals were collected at the pump, and washed with a little ether. These crystals were then boiled with ethyl acetate, when a small portion remained insoluble. The ethyl acetate insoluble portion was removed by filtration, and on crystallising twice from a mixture of chloroform and absolute alcohol, the m. p. was found to be $233^{\circ}-234^{\circ}$. Further crystallisations raised the m. p. to $238^{\circ}-239^{\circ}$. It formed small colourless rectangular plates.

It is not soluble in ether, petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, acetone. It is soluble in chloroform and sparingly in absolute alcohol, yield 0.01%. It is insoluble in dilute alkali and gives no colouration with ferric chloride, [Found: C, 70.25; H, 5.93; OMe, 22.7. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$: C, 70.58; H, 5.88; OMe, 22.8 per cent based on $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ (OMe)₂].

(2) The ethyl acetate solution was concentrated to a small volume, and cooled, the crystals which separated were collected and purified by recrystallisation once from benzene, and twice from ethyl acetate when the m. p. became constant at 113° (corrected), yield of aculeatin was 0.06%. Aculeatin forms colourless plates, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -16.8^{\circ}$. It is highly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, chloroform, alcohol, moderately soluble in ether, acetone and practically insoluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with orange colour. It is neutral to litmus and gives no colouration with ferric chloride and is also insoluble in 1% sodium hydroxide solution. [Found: C, 66.28; H, 6.18; OMe, 20.95; M.W (cryoscopic in benzene), 294; $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 66.20; H, 6.20; OMe, 21.30 per cent. M.W. 290].

(3) The oil left after the separation of the crops of crystals was subjected to steam distillation. A small amount of essential oil distilled over. The steaming was continued for 6 hours and the apparatus was allowed to stand over night. Next morning the yellow aqueous supernatant liquid was decanted out from the distilling flask and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath, when the residue became oily and highly viscous. This was cooled, scratched, adding a little ether from time to time. By this operation the viscous mass solidified gradually, but no crystals could be observed under microscope. This solidified mass was now introduced into a 100 c.c. conical flask, a little methyl alcohol added and allowed to stand over night. Next morning the solid was filtered at the pump and freed from adhering oil. The product was crystallised from chloroform, benzene, ethyl acetate and ultimately subjected to high vacuum distillation (170° - $180^{\circ}/0.1$ mm.) and the distilled product was again crystallised from benzene and ethyl acetate successively. Aculeatin hydrate, thus obtained, had m.p. 150° (corrected).

The oily residue left at the bottom of the steam-distillation flask was dissolved in a solvent (ether and a little methyl alcohol). This solution was allowed to stand for 3 days when a crop of crystal separated out. These crystals were also subjected to the same process of purification. It had m.p. 150° and was identical with aculeatin hydrate. The mother liquors from these two crops of crystals were allowed to stand in the cold, when another crop of crystals separated out; purified in the manner described above, it had the same m.p. of 150° . Mixed melting point was also exactly the same. The total yield of aculeatin hydrate (m.p. 150°) is 4.28 g. from 1 kg. of the stem bark; or 0.428%.

Aculeatin hydrate, thus purified (m.p. 150°), formed ill-defined prisms, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +50.9^{\circ}$ in chloroform solution. It is highly soluble in chloroform, and moderately in benzene and ethyl acetate, and practically insoluble in

petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with an orange colour, and gives no colouration with ferric chloride. It dissolves in 5% alkali and is precipitated unchanged by hydrochloric acid. (Found: C, 62.23; H, 6.41; OMe, 20.49. $C_{18}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 62.33; H, 6.49; OMe, 20.13 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Aculeatin: Formation of Aculeatin Hydrate.—In methyl alcoholic solution, aculeatin was hydrolysable in presence of 2*N*-sulphuric acid or alkali at the room temperature, but the hydrolysis was far from being complete. The following method was found suitable for the hydrolysis.

A solution of aculeatin (0.1 g.) in minimum quantity of rectified spirit was diluted with water (10 c.c.) and refluxed on a wire gauge for 8½ hours with two drops of sulphuric acid (2*N*). The clear solution was evaporated on water-bath until oily drops separated out. This was now cooled, and extracted with chloroform (twice) and also with ether (twice). These chloroform and ethereal extracts were washed with a little water separately. Finally the ethereal and the chloroform extracts were mixed together, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and evaporated nearly to dryness. The solid product, thus obtained, was twice crystallised from ethyl acetate, m. p. 149.5° (mixed m.p. with aculeatin hydrate remained undepressed), yield 0.052 g.

Diacetyl aculeatin hydrate was obtained from aculeatin hydrate as usual using acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. It crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 127°. [Found: OMe, 16.28. $(OMe)_2C_{14}H_{12}O_2(OAc)$, requires OMe, 15.82 per cent].

On deacetylation with alcoholic sodium hydroxide, it regenerated aculeatin hydrate, m.p. 149.5°.

Preparation of the Ketone $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$ from Aculeatin and Aculeatin Hydrate.—Aculeatin (0.1 g.) was heated with fused zinc chloride (1 g.) in a metal-bath at 140-45° for 1 hour. The mixture was poured into water containing a few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid and the whole was extracted with ether. Crystals were collected after concentrating the ethereal solution and purified by high vacuum distillation, m.p. 119.5°.

Aculeatin hydrate (0.3 g.) was heated with aqueous hydrochloric acid (2%, 5 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 140° for 4 hours. The product of reaction was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. The crystals were recrystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether and were distilled at 160-70°/0.1 mm., and finally recrystallised twice from ether,

m.p. 119-20° (corrected), yield 0.11 g. (Found: C, 66.15; H, 6.28. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$: C, 66.21; H, 6.21 per cent).

The ketone, prepared from a specimen of toddalolactone, melted at 119-120° (mixed m.p. of the two remained undepressed).

The semicarbazone of the ketone melted at 209° after recrystallisation from rectified spirit. (Found: N, 11.85. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{21}O_5N_3$: N, 12.1 per cent). The semicarbazone of the ketone obtained from Dey's toddalolactone also melted at 207.8° (mixed m.p. almost the same).

The *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazone of the ketone was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 9.97. $C_{22}H_{23}O_5N_3$ requires N, 9.88 per cent). The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone of the ketone obtained from Dey's toddalolactone had m.p. 210°, mixed m.p. same.

trans-Coumaric acid derivative of Aculeatin Hydrate.—Aculeatin hydrate (0.1 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c., 0.2 N) with a trace of mercuric oxide for 2 hours under reflux. The solution was filtered to remove mercuric oxide, and the filtrate was concentrated on a water-bath, cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was collected, washed with water and was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 170-171° (decomp.) [Found: C, 58.50; H, 6.8. $C_{18}H_{22}O_7$ requires C, 58.8; H, 6.75 per cent].

The acid phthalate of aculeatin hydrate was prepared as usual from aculeatin hydrate and phthalic anhydride by heating at 135° for 6 hours. After the reaction the mass was dissolved in dilute ammonia and extracted with chloroform to remove the unchanged aculeatin hydrate. The ammoniacal solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with chloroform. The acid phthalate, obtained by evaporating chloroform, was crystallised from 70% alcohol, m.p. 204°. (Found: C, 63.25; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{24}O_7$: C, 63.15; H, 5.26 per cent).

Oxidation of Aculeatin Hydrate with Cr_2O_3 .—A solution of aculeatin hydrate (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) with chromic acid (0.5 g.) dissolved in 20 c.c. of 50% acetic acid was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 60 hours in a well-stoppered flask. The reaction mixture was first distilled until 5 c.c. distillate were collected in a receiver containing 5 c.c. methyl alcohol (Merck), 4 drops of freshly distilled benzaldehyde and 4 drops of 10% sodium hydroxide solution. Due to the presence of acetic acid carried over during the distillation, the expected condensation did not occur. Hence this distillate was treated with calcium carbonate to eliminate the acetic acid and distilled again. The distillate (5 c.c.) was collected and made alkaline with 3 drops of 10% sodium hydroxide solution when dibenzalacetone separated in fine needles; recrystallised from 50%

methyl alcohol, m. p. $111^{\circ}5-112^{\circ}$, and identified as dibenzalacetone by mixed melting point.

Oxidation of Aculeatin Hydrate to the Aldehyde, $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ by Lead Tetraacetate.—A solution of aculeatin hydrate (0.45 g.) in glacial acetic acid (7 c.c.) and a solution of lead tetraacetate (0.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) were allowed to stand for 17 hours at the room temperature, and finally warmed to 40° for 15 minutes. Water (10 c.c.) was then added and the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and 10 c.c. water again added, when crystals separated. These were filtered at the pump, and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. $142-142.5^{\circ}$ (corrected). It distilled at $150-160^{\circ}/0.1$ m.m. (Found: C, 62.76; H, 5.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.90; H, 4.83 per cent).

The aldehyde, prepared from toddalolactone, also melts at $141.5^{\circ}-142.5^{\circ}$ (mixed m.p.)

My grateful thanks are due to Dr. P. K. Bose for his kind interest and encouragement during the course of these investigations and also placing the resources of his laboratory at my disposal.

My thanks are also due to Mr. N. N. Ghosh, M.Sc. for micro-analysis of some of the compounds.

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Received May 4, 1942.